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Mechanisms by which tumors promote their survival: active and direct or active and indirect.

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Our aim was to understand and describe the range of active and indirect mechanisms that cancer cells and the tumor use to support organismal survival to an extent that ultimately and nearly universally results in death of the host. These mechanisms are essentially different, with active mechanisms indicating a more sophisticated or higher level of subversive survival-promoting tumor behavior.

1 Aim: Understand that active and indirect mechanisms are essentially different and indicate a more
2 sophisticated or higher level of subversive survival-promoting tumor behavior.

3 Active and direct: Triple negative breast cancers up-regulate FGFR3 to support growth factor signaling.

4 Tumor evolution to promote (likely epigenetic) enhancement of receptor expression from the fibroblast
5 growth factor family is active, and direct: this promotes growth (which here is equivalent to survival) of the
6 cancer cell / tumor clone.

7 Active and indirect: Solid tumors up-regulate expression multi-drug resistance pumps encoded by genes
8 of the ATP-binding cassette family in response to chemotherapy to prevent their death following exposure
9 to toxic chemotherapies (xenobiotics) by actively pumping the drug out of the cancer cell.

10 The function of the pump, output of the catalytic site/ATP-binding domain of ATP-binding cassettes does
11 not in and of itself promote survival of the cancer cell. However, the function of the pump does prevent its
12 exposure to chemotherapy, which results in its death, and thus this is an active but indirect mechanism by
13 which the tumor promotes its survival.

14 Enhanced active and indirect mechanism: ABCF1

15 GSE120566

16 Transient expression of wild-type and mutant KRas G12V results in transcriptional activation of ABCF1 in
17 vitro, in the absence of tumor evolution (clonal selection that results in increased expression of ABCF1
18 through epigenetic mechanisms to promote survival of a clone with greater fitness).

19 ABCF1 function is associated with increased drug efflux and multidrug resistance.

20 Citation

21 Fung, S.W., Cheung, P.F.Y., Yip, C.W., Ng, L.W.C., Cheung, T.T., Chong, C.C.N., Lee, C., Bo-San Lai, P.,
22 Chan, A.W.H., Tsao, G.S.W. and Wong, C.H., 2019. The ATP-binding cassette transporter ABCF1 is a
23 hepatic oncofetal protein that promotes chemoresistance, EMT and cancer stemness in hepatocellular
24 carcinoma. Cancer letters, 457, pp.98-109.